

 NTICS 25

CONFERENCE PROCEEDINGS OF THE 2ND INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON NEW TRENDS IN COMPUTER SCIENCE

 November 15, 2025

 Lecture hall G, FSO, Morocco

For more information :
<https://ntics25-fso.ump.ma>

About NTICS25:

The 2nd International Conference on New Trends in Computer Science (NTICS25) will take place on November 15 at the Faculty of Sciences, Mohammed First University in Oujda, Morocco.

This prestigious event will bring together leading experts, researchers, and industry professionals from around the world to explore cutting-edge developments in Artificial Intelligence (AI), the Internet of Things (IoT), and other emerging technologies. NTICS25 serves as a vital platform for fostering innovation, collaboration, and knowledge exchange in these rapidly evolving fields.

Topics:

Artificial Intelligence and Applications

- Applications of AI and deep learning in computer vision, natural language processing, and autonomous systems
- Ethical and technical challenges in using AI for critical domains
- Meta-heuristic Optimization Techniques
- Machine and Deep Learning
- Combinatorial Optimization, Operational Research
- Dynamic/Continuous/Multi-Objective Optimization
- Fuzzy and Expert Systems
- AI Applications for Mobile Communication
- AI for eHealth
- AI Mobility
- AI for Services Applications and Emerging Topics
- AI for Image Processing and Multimedia
- AI for Control and Decision Systems
- AI for Energy, Computer Systems and Semiconductor Device
- AI for Industrial Applications
- AI for Enterprise, Economics, Commerce and Marketing
- AI for Water Management
- Social Media Features
- Social Impact of AI
- Sentiment Analysis

Internet of Things (IoT) and Smart Cities

- Integration of IoT and AI for managing urban infrastructure (energy, transportation, etc.)
- Security and interoperability challenges in complex IoT ecosystems
- Robotics & Drones
- Smart cities, Smart Grid & Industry 4.0

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- IoT, Edge/Fog Computing and Cloud
 - Intelligent embedded systems

New Generation Communication Networks, Cybersecurity and Blockchain

- Cybersecurity
- Blockchain for security
- 5G, 6G and beyond
- Vehicular and ad hoc networks
- Green Networking
- Systems and software security
- Advanced and post-quantum cryptography
- Privacy and confidentiality
- Safety in AI and AI for safety
- Cyber-resilience and business continuity

Databases and Information Systems: Analysis, Specification and Integration

- Requirement Engineering and Information Modelling Concepts
- Foundations and Concept Formalization for Database Schemas
- Distributed Database Systems and Mobile Database Applications
- Big Data, Data Warehouses, and Business Intelligence
- Knowledge Management Systems, Data mining and Knowledge discovery

Organizing Committee:

- Pr. Karima AISSAOUI
- Pr. Sanae MAZOUZ
- Pr. Ibtissam ARRASSEN
- Pr. Achraf BERRAJAA
- Pr. Soufiane DAHMANI
- Pr. Ayyoub EL OUTMANI

Keynote Speakers:

- Pr. Maha GMIRA
- Pr. Azzeddine MAZROUI

Website:

<https://ntics25-fso.ump.ma/>

Keynote Lecture Topics:

1. Evolving Paradigms in Arabic Morphological Disambiguation: From Machine Learning to Deep Learning

- **Pr. Azzedine Mazroui**
- **Abstract:** This presentation explores the major methodological shifts that have shaped computational approaches to Arabic language processing. It begins with an overview of Natural Language Processing (NLP), outlining its goals and relevance to linguistic research. The talk then examines the specific challenges of Arabic morphological analysis, emphasizing the structural richness and complexity of the language. Special attention is given to the sources of ambiguity in Arabic morphology, such as non-vocalized text and the multiplicity of possible word forms. The presentation further reviews the evolution of disambiguation techniques, tracing the transition from traditional Machine Learning models—including probabilistic and feature-based approaches—to Deep Learning architectures that leverage neural embeddings and contextual representations. Through this comparative perspective, the talk highlights how deep learning has transformed morphological disambiguation, improving accuracy and adaptability while opening new directions for research in Arabic NLP.
- **Short CV**
 - **Name:** MAZROUI Azzeddine
 - **Profession:** Full Professor at University Mohammed First, Faculty of sciences, Oujda, Morocco
 - **E-mail:** azze.mazroui@gmail.com
 - Member of the LaRI (Laboratory of Researches in Computer Sciences)
 - Director of the ANLP unit in the LaRI laboratory
 - Associate Editor for the Journal of King Saud University - Computer and Information Sciences

2. Generative AI: Some Applications

- **Pr. Maha GMIRA**
- **Abstract:** Generative Artificial Intelligence (AI) has emerged as one of the most transformative technologies of the past decade, enabling machines to create text, images, music, and even code that rival human creativity. Powered by deep learning architectures such as Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) and Large Language Models (LLMs), generative AI is revolutionizing diverse fields—from education and healthcare to design, software development, and scientific research.

This keynote explores the core principles behind generative AI systems and illustrates their practical applications across multiple domains. It also discusses the challenges associated with bias, interpretability, and ethical implications, emphasizing the importance of responsible development and deployment. The presentation concludes with perspectives on future directions and the potential impact of generative AI on innovation and human productivity.

- **Biography**

Dr. Maha Gmira is the Chief Technology Officer at Solution AI.

She previously served as an Artificial Intelligence Expert for the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP).

Before that, Prof. Maha Gmira was the Director of the School of Digital Engineering and Artificial Intelligence (EIDIA) at the Euromed University of Fes, and the holder of the ICESCO-UEMF Chair “Women in Science: Artificial Intelligence and the Future”, which promotes AI education and engagement among girls and women.

Maha Gmira graduated from Polytechnique Montréal, where she earned a Master’s degree in Mathematics and Industrial Engineering, followed by a Ph.D. in Artificial Intelligence.

In November 2021, the African Scientific Research and Innovation Council (ASRIC), a body of the African Union, awarded Prof. Maha Gmira a Flagship Project—a pilot initiative in Africa focusing on the application of artificial intelligence in agriculture to ensure food security across the continent. The project is led by Morocco in collaboration with Rwanda, Egypt, Botswana, and Nigeria.

In September 2022, she obtained a Horizon Europe project titled “REMARKABLE – Rural Environmental Monitoring via ultra-wide-Area networks and distributed federated Learning”, as part of a consortium of 12 countries, with a total budget of €1.4 million.

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A Review of Machine Learning Classification Approaches and Resampling Strategies for Imbalanced Datasets in Autism Spectrum Disorder

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ABSTRACT

Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) is often accompanied with severe communication difficulties. Lots of people depend more on gestures and pointing and other nonverbal communication rather than on fluent speech so it cannot be easy to deduce what is needed by families and caregivers. These barriers can be significantly decreased through early identification and providing supports, which are timely and tailored. To this end, assistive technologies, especially those that use machine-learning algorithms, can supplement clinical evaluation, increase diagnostic accuracy, and, ultimately, contribute to the improvement of the quality of life of ASD patients and caregivers. However, one of the persistent challenges in ASD-related research is data imbalance, where the number of ASD-positive cases is considerably smaller than non-target cases, leading to biased models and reduced sensitivity. To address this issue, resampling methods such as oversampling, under-sampling, and hybrid approaches have been combined with various classification techniques to enhance fairness and predictive reliability. By synthesizing the existing body of knowledge on both classification and resampling strategies. This research provides a narrative review of Machine Learning approaches for ASD, identifying key research trends, classifying existing methods, and evaluating their performance using metrics such as accuracy and sensitivity. At the same time, it examines the role of resampling methods such as oversampling, under sampling, and hybrid strategies—in addressing data imbalance, which can bias predictive models and reduce sensitivity.

Keywords: Autism Spectrum Disorder, Autism, ASD, ML, Machine Learning, Detection, Classification, Imbalanced Datasets, Resampling Strategies, Oversampling, Under-sampling.

A Tale of Two NLP Lexicons: A Comparative Walkthrough of TextBlob- and VADER-Based Sentiment Analysis

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ABSTRACT

Sentiment analysis (SA), a cornerstone of natural language processing (NLP), enables the systematic identification, extraction, and quantification of affective states and subjective information from textual data. This paper provides a comprehensive comparison of two widely adopted lexicon-based SA tools in Python: TextBlob and VADER (Valence Aware Dictionary and sentiment Reasoner). TextBlob, a versatile NLP library, offers SA alongside other functionalities, producing polarity (positive, negative, neutral scores) and subjectivity scores. Of note, polarity scores range from -1 to +1 while subjectivity scores range from 0 to 1, indicating objective to subjective text. In contrast, VADER is specifically engineered for SA of social media texts, delivering detailed probabilities for positive, negative, neutral sentiments, and compound scores (-1 to +1) that account for the unique linguistic features of social media communication. This analysis explores their methodologies, outputs, performance across hypothetical textual data, and suitability for different applications, highlighting their strengths and limitations. The findings suggest and reiterate that VADER is superior for social media analysis due to its ability to interpret contextual cues like emojis and punctuation, while TextBlob is more suitable for general text analysis and may not capture the nuances of social media language. VADER demonstrated superior performance across all primary metrics with an overall accuracy of 80.0%, with a weighted F1-Score of 0.76, while TextBlob achieved a significantly lower accuracy of 60.0% and a weighted F1-Score of 0.58. However, both tools exhibited limitations in domain-specific contexts, such as health related data, underscoring the need for tailored approaches in specialized domains and the potential of machine learning and deep learning methods.

Keywords: Natural language processing, Sentiment analysis, TextBlob, VADER, Comparison.

Advanced Control and Artificial Intelligence for Multi-Motor Electric Vehicles: A Bibliometric and Systematic Literature Review (2015–2025)

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a systematic literature review (SLR) of advanced control and artificial intelligence (AI) strategies for multi-motor electric vehicles (MMEVs) from 2015 to 2025. Following PRISMA and Kitchenham guidelines, 922 records were collected in Scopus and screened down to 52 primary studies. We synthesize control-oriented methods (MPC, SMC, robust/adaptive, FTC) and AI-oriented approaches (NN/DL, RL, fuzzy/ANFIS, heuristics), and analyze recent hybrid integrations (e.g., RL+MPC, SMC+Fuzzy, MPC+NN surrogates). We highlight performance–complexity trade-offs, embedded feasibility, and safety issues, and outline design patterns and evaluation practices to guide future research.

Keywords: Multi-motor EVs, Torque vectoring, Model Predictive Control, Sliding Mode Control, Reinforcement Learning, Hybrid control, Systematic Literature Review

Advances in 2D and 3D Facial Recognition technologies (1993–2025): A Bibliometric Analysis

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ABSTRACT

Since the early 1990s, facial recognition technology has advanced significantly, moving from conventional 2D image analysis to increasingly complex 3D facial modeling and deep learning-based systems. A thorough summary of the research output pertaining to 2D and 3D facial recognition technologies from 1993 to 2025 is given by this bibliometric analysis. We discovered publication patterns, major contributing nations, top universities, significant authors, and new research topics using the OpenAlex database and the R-based biblioshiny interface. The findings show that after 2010, research production increased quickly, with a significant focus on machine learning, biometrics, and real-time recognition, as well as an increase in international collaboration. We also draw attention to the rise of multi-disciplinary methods that combine artificial intelligence, psychology, and neuroscience.

Keywords: Facial Recognition, 2D Face Recognition, 3D Face Recognition, Deep Learning, Convolutional Neural Networks, Computer Vision, Biometrics

AI-Driven Consumer Behavior Prediction: A Data-Driven Framework for Digital Commerce and Marketing

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ABSTRACT

The process of consumer buying has become more complicated in the digital commerce age where businesses should use enhanced technology to stay competitive. This paper hypothesizes a data-driven predictive model of consumer behavior based on UCI Online Retail Dataset (2010-2011), which consists of more than 540,000 real consumer online e-commerce transactions. Our use of artificial intelligence (AI) tools to derive the utilization patterns of consumer purchase frequency, spending and recency facilitates customer segmentation, prediction and targeted marketing. The feature engineering in our methodology will combine with RFM (Recency, Frequency, and Monetary) modeling, customer segmentation modeling by clustering, purchase prediction modeling by classification, and demand prediction modeling. The accuracy, precision, recall and clustering validity indices are used to evaluate the results. The results are relevant to the domain of academics and practice as they show that AI-based models are more effective than classical statistical methods, as well as provide practical recommendations to be made when it comes to customized marketing and decision-making in the enterprise.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence · Consumer Behavior Prediction · E-Commerce · Customer Segmentation · Data-Driven Marketing

AI-Driven Time-Series Prognostics with Explainability for Turbofan Engines on C-MAPSS

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ABSTRACT

This paper addresses the prediction of remaining useful life (RUL) for turbofan engines using the C-MAPSS benchmark. We develop a compact hybrid model combining convolutional layers, LSTM, and multi-head attention to capture both local sensor patterns and long-term temporal dependencies. The data pipeline includes constructing RUL targets followed by a capping protocol, exponential smoothing, feature selection, min-max scaling, and fixed-length windowing with left padding, all under leakage-safe, engine-disjoint splits. Model selection follows a two-stage process: interface screening to identify the optimal window configuration, followed by Hyperband-based tuning of the architecture and optimizer. The final system is trained on the majority of non-test engines and evaluated once on held-out units. The model demonstrates strong performance across all C-MAPSS subsets and maintains interpretability through post-hoc attribution via Integrated Gradients. Results suggest that careful data handling, combined with a lightweight hybrid architecture, can yield accurate and explainable RUL estimates across diverse operating regimes.

Keywords: Remaining useful life; deep learning; turbofan engines; prognostics; C-MAPSS; interpretability

An enhanced CNN-based Intrusion Detection System for detecting anomalies in IoT networks

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ABSTRACT

The rapid growth of the Internet of Things (IoT) has created new possibilities for innovation in various fields, including smart homes, healthcare, industrial systems, and transportation. However, this growth has also increased the attack surface for cybercriminals. Traditional intrusion detection systems (IDS) face difficulties in handling the large volume, variety, and rapidly changing nature of IoT network traffic. In this paper, we propose a deep learning-based approach leveraging Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) to accurately detect malicious activities from IoT network. Using ToNIoT dataset, we evaluate the effectiveness of the proposed CNN model. Experimental results demonstrate that the CNN achieves high detection accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score, outperforming similar approaches.

Keywords: Internet of Things (IoT), Intrusion Detection System (IDS), Deep Learning (DL), Convolutional Neural Network (CNN).

Anatomical-Based Prediction of the Dose-Limiting Organ-at-Risk in Glioblastoma VMAT Planning: A Multi-Class Machine Learning Approach

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ABSTRACT

A primary challenge in VMAT planning for glioblastoma (GBM) is identifying which organ-at-risk (OAR) will be the most difficult to spare. This study introduces the Target OAR Prioritization for Planning (TOP-Plan) framework, a machine learning approach to predict the primary dose-limiting OAR (pDLO) from pre-treatment anatomy and to analyze its impact on final plan complexity. A cohort of 40 GBM VMAT plans from a public archive was analyzed. The ground-truth pDLO for each patient was defined geometrically as the OAR with the smallest surface-to-surface distance to the PTV. A feature vector, including PTV volume and PTV-to-OAR distances, was used to train a Random Forest classifier. A unifying analysis then linked the identified pDLO to the final plan Modulation Complexity Score (MCS). The analysis revealed a pronounced class imbalance, with the Brainstem comprising 75% of all pDLO cases. The trained classifier achieved an overall accuracy of 72.7%, demonstrating high proficiency in identifying the dominant Brainstem class but limited performance on rarer cases. Critically, the unifying analysis confirmed that Brainstem-limited cases were correlated with significantly higher final plan MCS values, indicating greater plan complexity. The TOP-Plan framework provides an interpretable tool that successfully identified the PTV-Brainstem interface as the dominant geometric driver of both planning challenges and subsequent plan complexity in GBM radiotherapy. This offers a valuable a priori stratification tool for managing clinical workflow and anticipating plan deliverability issues.

Keywords: Machine Learning, Radiotherapy, VMAT, Organs-at-Risk, Glioblastoma, Predictive Modeling, Treatment Planning.

AnomalousZ: Deep Autoencoder-Based Anomaly Detection in Lithium-Ion Batteries

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ABSTRACT

Lithium-ion batteries have become central to modern energy systems owing to their high energy density, efficiency, and adaptability across diverse applications. However, their complex electrochemical dynamics make them susceptible to faults induced by aging, thermal effects, and electrical stresses, raising significant safety and reliability concerns. This paper introduces a novel unsupervised anomaly detection framework for lithium-ion batteries, built upon deep AutoEncoder (AE) models and enhanced through a hybrid scoring mechanism that fuses reconstruction loss with Z-score-based statistical outlier detection.

A comprehensive dataset of four commercial-grade cells was analyzed, where engineered temporal features (e.g., capacity variation, terminal voltage fluctuation, and load response) were leveraged to capture subtle degradation dynamics. The AE-derived reconstruction errors were integrated with Z-score metrics to generate robust hybrid anomaly scores, enabling accurate identification of abnormal behavior under real-world conditions. Experimental evaluation demonstrated strong detection capability, identifying 770 anomalous events, with validation through synthetic anomaly injection and benchmarking confirming superior robustness and reliability. Furthermore, explainability analysis using SHAP highlighted the framework's reliance on physically meaningful features, reinforcing its interpretability. The proposed approach offers a scalable and effective pathway for real-time unsupervised anomaly detection in lithium-ion battery systems, supporting safer operation, predictive maintenance, and extended battery lifetime.

Keywords: Lithium-Ion Batteries; Anomaly Detection; Deep Learning; AutoEncoders; Explainable Artificial Intelligence; Feature Engineering

Application of Computer Vision and Artificial Intelligence for Automated Monitoring and Early Detection of Crop Diseases in the Context of Smart Agriculture

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ABSTRACT

Modern agriculture faces numerous challenges related to climate change, the depletion of natural resources, and the increasing global demand for food. Among these challenges, crop diseases represent a major cause of yield losses, threatening food security and the sustainability of agricultural systems. Traditional detection methods still rely largely on manual visual inspections, which are often time-consuming, costly, and prone to human error. In this context, recent advances in computer vision and Artificial Intelligence (AI) offer new opportunities to automate crop monitoring and enable early detection of pathological symptoms, thereby contributing to the development of a more efficient and sustainable form of Smart Agriculture. The main objective of this research is to design and develop an intelligent system for the detection and monitoring of crop diseases based on AI and computer vision techniques. Specifically, this work aims to develop a deep learning model capable of identifying different types of diseases from plant images, to integrate this model into an intelligent monitoring platform enabling real-time tracking using sensors, cameras, or drones, and to enhance agricultural decision-making by providing early alerts and actionable insights to farmers. The research focuses on four main areas: acquisition and preprocessing of visual data through the creation of an image database from various crops and segmentation of regions of interest; modeling and deep learning, by exploring architectures such as Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) and Vision Transformers (ViT) for disease classification and detection; the design of an intelligent monitoring system integrating AI models with IoT devices (sensors, drones) for automated field monitoring; and finally, system evaluation and validation by analyzing model performance in terms of accuracy, robustness, and interpretability using real-world data. This research aims to contribute to food security and environmental sustainability by harnessing the potential of artificial intelligence and computer vision to transform the way crop diseases are detected, monitored, and managed.

Keywords: Smart Agriculture, Computer Vision, Deep Learning, Disease Detection, Artificial Intelligence, IoT.

Assessment of Process Management and Maturity in Public Hospitals: An Explainable Machine Learning Approach

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ABSTRACT

With a view to improving their performance, public hospitals, particularly in Morocco, have begun to adopt certain management tools inspired by the private sector. In this research, we sought to assess the process management maturity level in Moroccan public hospitals and to predict areas for improvement to achieve a high level of maturity. To this end, we relied on the Business Process Orientation Maturity Model (BPOMM) as a reference framework. To deepen our analysis and identify potential areas for improvement, we employed ML algorithms, specifically Random Forest Classifier and XGBoost.

The main results show that the current maturity level of prefectural and provincial hospitals (1st and 2nd level) is below 2 (Maturity Level <2). Meanwhile, university hospitals (3rd level) recorded a current maturity level above 2 (Maturity Level ≥ 2). The application of explainable AI (XAI) methods, particularly SHAP, revealed that both algorithms converged on the same priority areas. Socio-economic and operational performance (SEOP) and optimization: action plan and performance measurement (OAPM), emerged as the most decisive for reaching level 3. In addition, the vision process (VP) and risk management and compliance control (RMCC) also stand out for their significant influence, although less marked than the two main areas.

Keywords: Maturity, Management, Machine learning, Explainability, Public hospitals, Morocco.

Artificial Intelligence for Predicting Postoperative Complications: A Case Study from Moroccan Healthcare

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ABSTRACT

This paper explores the use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) to predict postoperative complications in surgical patients, with a particular focus on healthcare settings in Morocco. The aim is to leverage machine learning models trained on clinical and perioperative data to identify patients at higher risk of complications, thereby enabling early intervention and improving patient outcomes. The integration of Internet of Things (IoT) technologies is also considered to enhance real-time data collection and monitoring. Preliminary results highlight the potential of AI-based predictive models to assist surgeons and anesthesiologists in clinical decision-making.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence · Postoperative Complications · Healthcare · Prediction · Internet of Things · Morocco

Benchmarking Deep Learning Algorithms for Lip-Reading and Face Detection in Personalized E-Learning Systems

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ABSTRACT

The incorporation of advanced human-computer interaction (HCI) techniques into E-Learning and teaching Systems has the potential to significantly enhance learning experiences through personalization. This paper offers a thorough benchmarking study focusing on cutting-edge lip-reading and face-detection algorithms, assessing their performance in optimizing these systems.

We conduct a detailed analysis and comparison of the robustness and computational efficiency of various widely used deep learning-based algorithms designed for lip-reading and face detection.

The insights derived from this benchmarking exercise are then utilized to pinpoint the most suitable algorithmic choices for specific E-Learning and Teaching Systems scenarios.

Additionally, the study highlights key challenges and outlines future research directions aimed at improving the performance and applicability of lip-reading and face-detection algorithms in the dynamic and complex environments of these systems.

Keywords: Face detection; Lip; reading; eLearning systems; Deep Learning; Haar Cas; cade; MTCNN; YOLO; SSD.

Comparative Study of Common Models for Automatic Polyp Detection and Segmentation in Endoscopic Images

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ABSTRACT

Colorectal cancer remains a predominant contributor to global cancer mortality. The timely detection and resection of polyps during colonoscopic procedures are fundamental to effective preventive strategies. However, manual detection is often challenging, as polyps exhibit substantial variability in size, shape, and visual appearance. These difficulties underline the importance of developing computer-aided diagnosis (CAD) systems to support clinicians in the detection process. Deep learning has advanced automatic polyp detection and segmentation, but comparative evaluations that inform clinical deployment are scarce. This study provides a comprehensive evaluation of prominent models for automated polyp identification and segmentation in endoscopic imagery. We evaluate segmentation architectures (U-Net, SegNet, N-Net, Dilated-U-Net-Seg) and a detection framework (YOLOv8), tested on the Kvasir dataset. The analysis emphasizes the balance between segmentation accuracy, computational demands, and detection speed, providing practical guidelines for building reliable CAD systems in gastrointestinal endoscopy.

Keywords: Polyp Detection · Deep Learning, U-Net, Seg-Net, N-Net, Dilated-U-Net-Seg · YOLOv8, Medical Image Analysis, Endoscopy

Datasets and Techniques for Cardiovascular Disease Prediction: A Review

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ABSTRACT

Heart disease or Cardiovascular illness (CVD) is one of the most cause of mortality globally, With an estimated 18 million deaths each year. Machine learning (ML) and Deep Learning (DL) models can detect early signs of CVD from clinical datasets and physiological signal data, helping to reduce mortality rates. Numerous datasets are available for cardiovascular disease prediction, including Cleveland, Framingham, MIT-BIH, PTB-XL... These datasets differ in the type of data; some contain structured clinical information while other focus on physiological recordings. In this review, we provide an overview of essential datasets frequently employed in cardiovascular disease prediction, highlighting the characteristics and structure of each dataset. Then we examine how these datasets have been implemented in ML and DL approaches. This review aims to explore dataset characteristics, and evaluate the performance of ML and DL models. It offers a guide for researchers to improve heart disease prediction systems.

Keywords: Heart disease; Heart Disease Prediction; Machine learning; Deep learning; Clinical Data Analysis; PTB; XL dataset; MIT; BIH Arrhythmia dataset.

From Black-Box to Explainability: Transforming Decision Support Systems with XAI

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ABSTRACT

Artificial intelligence (AI) is transforming the way decisions are made across various fields, offering powerful tools to analyze complex data, identify patterns, and generate recommendations. AI-powered decision support systems (DSS) provide significant advantages, but the "black-box" nature of traditional AI models can make their outcomes difficult to interpret, leading to reduced user trust. This paper explores how Explainable AI (XAI) can enhance DSS by making AI-driven decisions more transparent and understandable. We discuss the benefits of XAI, such as AI transparency, increased user confidence, and more effective decision-making. Additionally, we examine different XAI techniques designed to improve model interpretability, distinguishing between model-agnostic and model-specific approaches. These methods help bridge the gap between users and AI, fostering a more intuitive and collaborative interaction. Finally, we explore the challenges and future directions of human-centered AI, emphasizing its potential to reshape data-driven decision-making.

Keywords: Explainable AI (XAI); Decision Support Systems (DSS); AI Transparency; Model Interpretability; Human; Centered AI

From Prediction to Explanation in HRM Decision Making: A Transparent Approach to Employee Overtime Analytics

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ABSTRACT

Strategic decision-making in organizations increasingly relies on data-driven insights, yet the opacity of complex predictive models limits their adoption by managers. This paper proposes and evaluates a predictive and explainable system designed to support strategic decision-making in the context of employee overtime behavior evaluation. Using a case study based on organizational workforce data, we develop a machine-learning model to forecast employee overtime behavior and integrate state-of-the-art explainable artificial intelligence (XAI) techniques by leveraging structured HR data and combining high-performance models such as Logistic Regression and CatBoost with interpretability tools, including SHAP and LIME, to make model outputs transparent and actionable. We assess the system on predictive accuracy, stability of explanations across employee segments, and perceived usefulness for decision-makers. Results demonstrate that combining predictive analytics with explainability improves both the quality and trustworthiness of insights delivered to HR and strategic managers. The study contributes a replicable framework for integrating XAI into predictive decision support systems and outlines implications for organizational governance, fairness, and future research on explainable strategic decision-making.

Keywords: Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI); Predictive Modeling; Decision Making; Human Resource Management (HRM); Overtime Analytics; Transparency

Comparative Evaluation of Machine Learning and Deep Learning Models for Global Horizontal Irradiance Forecasting in Morocco

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ABSTRACT

Solar energy is rapidly growing as a sustainable and environmentally friendly alternative to meet growing energy demand while reducing dependence on fossil fuels and greenhouse gas emissions. The installation of photovoltaic systems has multiplied in the residential and commercial sectors as well as in large solar parks. Forecasting global horizontal irradiation (GHI) is essential, as it is the key variable for estimating photovoltaic production. However, GHI is highly dependent on climatic conditions, making it difficult to predict. This study compares five machine learning methods for GHI forecasting in Morocco, namely convolutional neural networks (CNN), support vector regression (SVR), random forests (RF), long short-term memory (LSTM) and artificial neural networks (ANN) using NSRDB data covering January to December 2022. The models were evaluated according to the coefficient of determination R^2 , the root mean square error RMSE, and the mean absolute error MAE. The results indicate that ANN offers the best accuracy, with the lowest errors and the highest R^2 . This performance confirms its effectiveness and provides useful insights for optimizing photovoltaic systems and integrating them into predictive maintenance solutions.

Keywords: Machine Learning, Global Horizontal Irradiation (GHI), Renewable Energy, Solar Forecasting, Artificial Intelligence.

Harnessing LLMs and Generative AI for Detecting and Generating Scientific Content

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ABSTRACT

Generative Artificial Intelligence (GenAI) in the form of Large Language Models (LLMs) has revolutionized the way that scientists interact with scholarly writing. They enable the creation of quality texts, making plagiarism detection a crucial field for human beings. This progress involves the creation of a powered Artificial Intelligence (AI) detection methods. Additionally, the use of LLMs to scientific content creation by helping in manuscript writing, research summaries and even generating hypotheses. AI application in both stages of generation and verification of scholarly material requires a methodical examination of available methods and limitations in this field. This research carries out a Systematic Literature Review of 58 studies to examine the methods, datasets and evaluation techniques applied in their integration within scientific writing. The results list ways of using LLMs in academic research like framework development, as well as the need of overcoming challenges such as hallucinations. The findings highlight the demand for stronger systems of evaluation, better AI detection software and more detailed ethical guidelines for responsible use of LLMs within the academic field. This review is contributing to the discussions of the future use of AI in academic communication, with descriptions of how LLMs are capable be effectively integrated while minimizing potential risks.

Keywords: Generative AI; LLMs; scientific writing; academic writing; AI detection; education.

LegalTech and Moroccan Law Modeling Automated Structuring and Splitting of Moroccan Legal Documents for Retrieval-Augmented Generation

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ABSTRACT

The accessibility and accuracy of Moroccan legal texts can be significantly improved through an AI-driven system. Many legal documents, especially those from the Bulletin Officiel (BO), are stored in scanned or poorly structured formats, which hinders their searchability and effective processing. This challenge is even greater for Arabic legal texts due to their linguistic complexity. While Large Language Models (LLMs) have proven to be powerful tools for generating insights, their utility is often limited when they do not have access to up-to-date external knowledge, which can result in outdated or hallucinated responses. To address these challenges, the application of Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) techniques is being explored. RAG combines LLMs with external knowledge sources to enhance the accuracy and contextual relevance of responses. This approach is particularly important for legal documents, where precision and context are paramount. Key aspects of this research include the analysis of content extraction methods for legal texts, with a focus on overcoming issues such as text fragmentation and inconsistent formatting. Additionally, chunking algorithms will be investigated to organize extracted content in a way that maintains the legal text's structure, coherence, and contextual integrity. The most appropriate chunking techniques for legal texts will be evaluated, considering factors such as document layout and content complexity.

Keywords: LegalTech, Large language models, Retrieval-augmented generation, Legal documents, Moroccan law, Document splitting, Chunking algorithms.

Post-Earthquake Monitoring of Building Cracks Using Deep-Learning (YOLOv10)

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ABSTRACT

This study focuses on the application of the YOLOv10 algorithm for post-seismic crack monitoring in buildings using deep learning techniques. The introduction presents a general overview of the YOLO (You Only Look Once) architecture. The results section provides a detailed description of the main components of YOLOv10, as well as the equations associated with the evaluation metrics used. Then, in the case study section, a dataset containing images of buildings affected by earthquake-induced cracks is used. Training the YOLOv10 model on this data yielded reliable results, characterized by good performance in terms of accuracy and detection efficiency. Finally, the discussion provides an analysis of the model's performance, highlighting the contribution of this work and future research opportunities.

Keywords: Earthquake; Deep Learning; Yolov10; Cracks; Prediction.

Real-Time Palm Tree Detection in RGB Drone Imagery Using Lightweight YOLOv12s Architecture

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a robust approach for palm tree detection in aerial imagery using the YOLOv12s model trained on high resolution RGB drone data. The proposed method achieves a precision of 95.7%, recall of 92.5%, and an F1-score of 94.1%. The mean average precision at 0.5 intersection over union (mAP@0.5) reaches 98.1%, while the stricter mAP@[0.5:0.95] is 64.1%. These results demonstrate the model's suitability for real-time deployment in precision agriculture, enabling accurate palm counting and inventory estimation using only standard RGB drone platforms—without requiring multispectral sensors or pixel-level annotations. This work contributes to applied artificial intelligence and data science by offering a practical, scalable solution for agricultural monitoring in resource-constrained settings.

Keywords: Palm tree detection; YOLOv12s; aerial imagery; precision agriculture; object detection

Similarity-Based Education Recommendation Systems: Assisting Teachers in Implementing Active Pedagogies

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ABSTRACT

Teaching at the Right Level (TARL) is a pedagogical approach aimed at enhancing foundational skills among students by grouping them according to their learning levels and utilizing engaging activities to foster active and individualized learning. However, teachers encounter challenges due to the heterogeneity of student abilities and large class sizes. Education based Recommendation Systems can offer valuable support in overcoming these challenges and assisting teachers in this process. By leveraging similarities between students and between proposed learning activities, we can develop effective systems. In this study, we aim to compare the performance of item-based collaborative filtering by merging similarities derived from student ratings with those calculated from course descriptions. We employed MAE (Mean Absolute Error) and MSRE (Mean Squared Relative Error) metrics to assess the performance of our model. The results indicate that similarities based on ratings assigned to courses by users yield positive outcomes. In contrast, similarities derived from course descriptions tend to disrupt the model, regardless of the weight attributed to this similarity.

Keywords: TARL, Education based Recommendation Systems, Collaborative filtering, Similarity measures, Content based.

Smart Cattle Health Management with MobileNetV2: Disease Detection and Treatment Recommendation

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ABSTRACT

Agriculture forms the backbone of a nation's economy, supplying food, fiber, crops, and livestock, while generating employment and reducing poverty. In Morocco's Souss-Massa region, livestock production, particularly for milk and meat, plays a vital role. This project focuses on detecting cattle diseases and providing treatment recommendations using image processing techniques, integrated into a web platform developed with the Flask framework. Early identification of cattle diseases is crucial for farmers to minimize annual losses. Simulation results demonstrate that the network classifier achieves low training error and high classification accuracy. The model is intended to support farmers in timely disease detection, enabling prompt and effective treatment.

Keywords: Precision agriculture; cattle disease classification; Convolutional neural networks; treatment recommendation.

Survey: Advances and Challenges in Real-Time Multi-Human Tracking

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ABSTRACT

Multi-human tracking has emerged as a central task in computer vision with wide applications in surveillance, robotics, and human-computer interaction. It focuses on maintaining consistent identities of individuals across video frames, despite occlusions, illumination changes, and crowded scenes. Over the years, different paradigms have been developed to address these challenges. Early methods based on Discriminative Correlation Filters (DCF) offered efficiency but lacked robustness. Siamese networks introduced deep feature similarity learning for better person re-identification, while Transformer-based models recently achieved significant progress by modeling long-range dependencies and spatial-temporal relations. In this study, we evaluate 21 state-of-the-art trackers proposed over the past two years, selected for their strong impact and frequent adoption within the research community. This paper presents a concise survey of these three major approaches—DCF-based, Siamese-based, and Transformer-based tracking methods—highlighting their main contributions, advantages, and limitations. Open research challenges and future directions are also discussed to guide further developments in multi-human tracking.

Keywords: Multi; human tracking; Discriminative Correlation Filters; Siamese Networks; Transformers; Computer Vision

Teachers and Technology Integration in the AI Era: A Digital Maturity Perspective

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ABSTRACT

The digital transformation of education demands a reassessment of teacher competencies. This article addresses the challenge of evaluating digital skills by proposing a novel, AI-powered framework for modeling teacher digital maturity. Moving beyond static models, our adaptive approach leverages machine learning and data analytics to provide personalized, dynamic assessment across technical, pedagogical, and ethical dimensions. We present the model's architecture and a preliminary case study, arguing that AI is a critical tool for diagnosing needs and guiding effective professional development in the AI era.

Keywords: Teacher Digital Maturity; Artificial Intelligence (AI) in Education; Digital Competence Framework; Professional Development; Educational Technology; AI; Powered Assessment; Personalized Learning

The Impact of Large Language Models on Financial Services: A Comprehensive Survey

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ABSTRACT

The financial industry has become a big fan of large language models because they allow them to change important business functions such as sentiment analysis, portfolio optimization and market forecasting. The results of 80 studies from 2019 to 2025 are based on practical use, trends, and challenges in the deployment of LLMs and generative AI in finance. This suggests that post-2023 research activity was growing tremendously, especially with new models such as GPT-4 and FinBERT. These technologies have been used in real-world applications such as regulatory automation and synthetic data generation to improve customer services with AI. But there are few problems that persist in relation to data bias, model interpretation difficulties, computational costs, output hallucinations and regulatory compliance. Finally, this paper concludes with recommendations on ethical AI implementation, including standard evaluation benchmarks, public data use, and improved model transparency.

Keywords: Large Language Models and Generative AI and Financial Technology and Algorithmic Trading and Investment

The Promises and Perils of Generative AI Adoption Across Domains

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ABSTRACT

This systematic literature review explores the impact of generative AI models on three key sectors: social media content, education and scientific writing/publishing. The rapid development and incorporation of AI technologies have led to a lot of interest for their capability to reshape age old processes in numerous fields. The purpose of this research is as generative AI takes on a bigger and bigger role in making personalized educational content, improving social media engagement, and tools in creative writing. This study aims at evaluating the effectiveness and consequences of these technologies, pinpointing the advantage and shortcomings the technology offers. While generative AI has the potential to transform personalized learning, content creation automation as well as science research assistance, it also has its own ethical dilemmas in terms of data privacy, misinformation, and academic integrity, the findings say. second, these findings underscore the need to develop guidelines to promote the safe and useful use of generative.

Keywords: Generative AI, Education, Social Media Content, Scientific Writing, Systematic Literature Review.

TinyML and XAI in Healthcare: Advances, Use Cases and Challenges

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ABSTRACT

In the medical sector, intelligent technologies are becoming crucial as they open new opportunities, improve diagnosis, and enhance patient care. Artificial Intelligence (AI), Machine Learning (ML), and Deep Learning (DL) are now widely used to provide more accurate and individualized tools for medical image analysis, disease prediction, and treatment optimization. Recent developments have demonstrated the possibilities of deploying ML models on ultra-low-power microcontrollers and integrating AI into medical devices with Tiny Machine Learning (TinyML). In parallel, Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI) has emerged as a key solution to improve transparency and trust in clinical decision-making by making AI outputs more interpretable for healthcare professionals. This study explores how ML, DL, TinyML, and XAI have developed in medicine, highlighting the benefits and real-world applications of each technology in healthcare. Finally, it discusses the challenges they face.

Keywords: AI; ML; DL; Medical sector; TinyML; XAI.

Architectural and Security Considerations in Modern Web Development with React and Next.js: SPA, SSR, SSG, and Server Actions

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ABSTRACT

Abstract. The evolution of web architectures from Multi-Page Applications (MPAs) to modern paradigms like Single-Page Applications (SPA), Server-Side Rendering (SSR), Static Site Generation (SSG), and Server Actions presents developers with complex trade-offs between performance, scalability, and security. This paper investigates these trade-offs and their security implications in the context of React and Next.js. The methodology is based on a comparative analysis of architectural models, supplemented by two real-world case studies developed during an internship at Smile Morocco for Orange Morocco: an internal SPA for client services and a public e-commerce platform using SSR/SSG. Key findings indicate that SPAs offer high interactivity but pose SEO and XSS risks, while SSR/SSG improve SEO and initial load performance at the cost of increased server complexity. Server Actions simplify development but require rigorous server-side security. The conclusion advocates for a hybrid architectural approach, leveraging innovations in React 19 and Next.js 15 like React Server Components and streaming, to build applications that are performant, scalable, and secure by design.

Keywords: Single Page Application (SPA), Server-Side Rendering (SSR), Static Site Generation (SSG), Server Actions, React 19, Next.js 15, React Server Components (RSC), Memoization, Streaming Rendering, Client Components, Server Components, Web Application Security, Performance Optimization, B2C E-commerce, Modern Web Architecture.